

Pre-Election Forecast

2026 Hungarian Parliamentary Election

Kristóf Andrási

Posted: April 11, 2026 — one day before the election

This document records the pre-election forecast produced as part of my MSc thesis in Social Data Science. It is uploaded before the April 12, 2026 election to establish an unmodifiable timestamp of the predictions. The full methodology, code and data are available on [GitHub](#).

Three forecast paths are reported below. The **primary forecast** is the simple weighted average with a 70% poll and 30% fundamentals combination, indicated in bold in all tables. The poll-only path shows the raw polling signal without any structural anchor. The house-effects corrected path adjusts for systematic pollster biases. The two combined paths agree closely on national vote shares. The main spread comes from the poll-only path, which carries no structural anchor.

Table 1: Combined national vote share forecast (%)

Path	Government	Opposition (TISZA)	Radical opp. (Mi Haz.)	Other
Simple weighted average — poll only	40.1	48.7	5.6	5.6
Simple weighted average — 70/30 (primary)	43.2	44.1	7.0	5.7
House effects RW — 70/30	43.4	44.0	7.8	4.7

Table 2: Expected seats from the 1,500-draw Monte Carlo simulation (out of 199 total seats)

Path	Government	Opposition (TISZA)	Radical opp. (Mi Haz.)	Other
Simple weighted average — poll only	84	106	9	0
Simple weighted average — 70/30 (primary)	95	90	14	0
House effects RW — 70/30	92	91	16	0

Table 3: Key scenario probabilities from the 1,500-draw Monte Carlo simulation (%)

Scenario	Poll only	70/30 simple (primary)	House eff. RW 70/30
Government finishes first in list share	18.9	46.6	51.2
Opposition finishes first in list share	81.1	53.4	48.8
Government majority (≥ 100 seats)	18.7	39.3	46.2
Government two-thirds (≥ 133 seats)	0.1	1.1	22.9
Opposition majority (≥ 100 seats)	64.3	29.7	42.3
Opposition two-thirds (≥ 133 seats)	7.1	1.4	23.6

The primary forecast is the simple weighted average with a 70% poll and 30% fundamentals combination. The full methodology and model selection rationale are documented in the thesis and on [GitHub](#). In short, this path remains the preferred basis for the 2026 forecast because it showed the strongest performance

across the LOEO backtest as a whole. Both alternative paths are presented as sensitivity checks. The poll-only path shows the raw polling signal without a structural anchor. The house-effects corrected path agrees closely with the primary forecast on vote shares but produces higher seat probabilities for the government due to its larger historical uncertainty bands. The central conclusion is that the race is too close to call.